

Increasing Agricultural Investments through Cost of Capital Deregulation in Nigeria

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Abstract

the study was conducted to examine increasing agricultural investments through the cost of capital deregulation in Nigeria, with the following specific objectives: ascertain the factors that determine aggregate credit volume of agricultural investment within the cost of regulated and deregulated periods and estimate the level of growth rate in agricultural financing in Nigeria before and after a deregulated period. Co-integration and Real Credit Growth Rate Model were used to realize the objectives respectively. The result showed that interest rate deregulation had a significant and positive impact on agricultural growth in Nigeria, co-integration relationship existed among the variables and average interest lending rate and government budget allocation were the significant variables that had a long-run effect on the aggregate credit volume. Result also showed that 92 % of the disequilibrium caused by previous year's shocks converges back to the long-run equilibrium in the current year. Credit volume of agriculture increases with a decrease in average interest lending rate, also agricultural credit growth rate increased in real terms at 8.91% under the period of study, more so, agricultural GDP contribution to Nigerian economy had a positive relationship with credit volume to agriculture. Finally, ACGSF and CBL were major determinants of the government finance interventions on the agricultural sector and its contribution to the GDP of the Nigerian economy. The following recommendations were proffered: interest rate should be reduced to at least 5% or any other single digit to stimulate investment in the agricultural sector and there should be proper implementation, coordination, and evaluation of financial policies in the agricultural sector.

Keywords: *interest rate, deregulation, agriculture, co-integration, credit volume.*

1.0 Introduction

The economic significance of the agricultural sector in Nigeria need not be overemphasized and hence concerns have developed over its growth and sustainability to guarantee this unique role (Ettah, Ettah, Kuye Oniah & Adinya, 2017). The relationship between financial development and agricultural growth has recently been suggested by experts and is in the front burner of economic discussions of developing countries like Nigeria (World Bank, 2008). Financial development in an economy in favour of the agricultural sector would entail reforming the cost of acquiring capital for agricultural purposes. The reforms are expected to encourage domestic savings and make loanable funds available to the banking institutions, the liberalization of the interest rate, collateral, guarantors, etc.

Idoko, Emmanuel and Kpeyo (2012) noted that there is an inverse relationship between agricultural investment and the cost of capital. This means that if the rate of the cost of capital is high agricultural investment would be low and vice versa. There is, therefore, need to promote an interest rate regime that would ensure inexpensive spending for agricultural investment. Government has been reluctant in allowing market forces to determine the rate of the cost of capital, in recognition of its importance in agricultural investment (Onyishi, Arene & Ifora, 2015). Ifeanyi and Chukwu (2014) opined that the government has always used such instruments like deregulation and guided regulation, to manipulate prevailing rates depending on the health of the economy.

This study focuses on deregulation, a common mechanism used in Nigeria. According to Ifebuolili (2014), financial deregulation represents a policy response, encompassing a package of measures to remove all undesirable government imposed constraints on the free working of the financial markets. The authors further asserted that deregulation is based on the assumption that "markets know best" and involves such

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controls like ceiling and loosening of deposits and credit controls. Cost of capital is the price paid for the use of money expressed in percentages. It is the opportunity cost of borrowing money from a lender to finance an investment project and also the returns being paid to the financial resources for foregoing the funds for future consumption, it is always expressed as a percentage rate. Obut, Adyorough & Itodo (2012) defined the cost of capital deregulation as an economic term used to refer to a situation whereby forces of demand and supply are allowed to determine the value of the rates rather than its value being administered directly by monetary authorities.

The study would benefit potential agricultural investors because interest rates play major roles and act as the deciding factor in making funds available for investment and also encourages savers to minimize their consumption levels thereby making investment funds available. The authors set to realize the following objectives:

- i. ascertain the factors that determine aggregate credit volume of agricultural investment within the cost of regulated and deregulated periods.
- ii. Estimate the level of growth rate in agricultural financing in Nigeria before and after the deregulated period.

The study is guided by this null hypothesis: therefore is no significant co-integrating relationship among the variables.

2.0 Methodology

2.1 Study area: the area of study in Nigeria, the area has a geographical area of 923,768 square kilometers and a population of about 167 million people (NPC, 2011). Nigeria is located in between latitude $4^{\circ} 16'$ and $13^{\circ} 53'$ North and longitude $2^{\circ} 40'$ and $14^{\circ} 41'$ respectively. The country is located within the tropics and therefore experiences high temperature in the greater part of the year. The mean temperature for the country is 27°C , with a climate varying from very wet coastal area with an annual rainfall greater than 3,500mm to the Sahel region in the Northwestern and Northeastern parts with an annual rainfall of less than 600mm (NEEDS, 2005). Nigeria is distinguished by the diversity of the ecosystem, an advantage for growing a wide range of crops. The main staple food crops produced include yam, cassava, rice, maize, sorghum, millet and livestock such as birds, cattle, goat, etc.

2.2 Data Collection and Analysis

Secondary data were used in the study and were collected from CBN statistical bulletin and annual reports of the apex bank, National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) annual report, etc. collected data were analysed with the use of statistical tools of Co-integration and Real Credit Growth Rate Model, to capture objectives I and ii respectively.

Model specification

Model for objective i

The factors that determine aggregate credit volume of agricultural investment within the cost of regulated and deregulated periods are given as $Y_t = b_0 + b_1X_{1t} + b_2X_{2t} + b_3X_{3t} + b_4X_{4t} + \dots + b_8X_{8t} + \sum_t$ (i)

where: Y_t = aggregate credit volume of agricultural investment in time t (ratio/%)

X_{1t} = average interest lending rate or cost of capital in time t (ratio/%)

X_{2t} = aggregate interest savings rate in time t (ratio/%)

X_{3t} = savings mobilized by financial institutions in time t (₦)

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X_{4t} = average inflation rate in time t (ratio/%)

X_{5t} = government budgetary allocation to agriculture (₦)

X_{6t} = credit to the private sector (Agric. and non-Agric.) in time t (₦)

X_{7t} = direct investment into Nigeria's economy in time t (₦)

X_{8t} = average exchange rate in time t (ratio/%)

b_0 = intercept point

$b_1, b_2, b_3, \dots, b_8$ = coefficients of the variable

the study adopted the Engle Granger (1987) two-step co-integration. Step one involved a preliminary analysis to find the order of integration of the data series, after which ordinary least square regression was carried out to estimate the equation for the aggregate where the integration can be found. These are the stationary (unit root) and co-integration test respectively. In the second stage, the residuals obtained in the long run co-integration regression was used as an explanatory variable to specify a dynamic error correction model, which was estimated through OLS regression.

Model for objective ii

The Real Growth Model modified from the study of Sa (2007) was used to estimate the level of growth rate in agricultural financing in Nigeria before and after the deregulated period. It is given as:

$$P_t = 100 \left(\frac{\frac{C_t}{C_{t-1}}}{1 + \pi_t} - 1 \right) \tag{ii}$$

Where: C_t = volume of the loan in time t

C_{t-1} = previous year volume of loan

π_t = inflation rate of a country in time t

3.0 Result and Discussion

3.1 Impact of interest rate deregulation policies on Nigeria's Agricultural growth

The study examined the effects of cost of capital or interest rate on agricultural growth in Nigeria from 1982-2017. The result of the study obtained showed that interest rate deregulation had a significant and positive impact on agricultural growth in Nigeria within the period under study. This implies that a unit increase in the cost of capital or interest rate will increase agricultural productivity by 1088.82. This result is in line with studies by Onyishi, Arene & Ifora (2015) and Ifeanyi and Chukwu (2014) whose results showed that interest rate deregulation had a significant positive relationship with the growth of Agricultural productivity in Nigeria. Theories explaining interest rate deregulation suggests that this phenomenon will promote required resource inflow into agriculture to enable it to achieve expected contributions to national development. Nevertheless, the results of this research did not agree with the study of Idoko *et. al.*, (2012) and Ifebuolili (2014). In their study, interest rate deregulation does not have a significant impact on the growth of Agricultural productivity in Nigeria.

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Table 1: Impact of interest rate deregulation policies on Nigeria's Agricultural growth

Variable	Co-efficient	Standard error	t-statistic
Constant	-1586.912	2435.950	-0.65
Interest rate	1088.816	355.67	3.061**
R ²	0.22		
Adj R ²	0.19		
F-statistics	9.37***		

Source: Computed from CBN data 2017. Statistical significant levels *** = 1%. ** =5%; * =10%

3.2 Factors that determine the aggregate credit volume of agriculture within the cost of capital regulated and deregulated periods

3.2.1 ADF test for stationarity (Unit root test)

Table 2 explains the summary statistics of the ADF test. The results of the test indicated that only one variable was stationary at level 1(0), while others were stationary at first difference. Specifically, average interest lending rate (X₁), average interest savings rate (X₂), savings mobilized by financial institutions (X₃), and government budget allocation (X₅), credit to private sector (X₆), direct investment into Nigeria's economy (X₇) and aggregate credit volume to agricultural (Y) were all stationary at first difference, while the average inflation rate (X₄) was stationary at level 1(0), The findings of the study provided the justification of ARDL Approach.

Table2: Results of ADF test

Variable	ADF(stat)	Variable (1 st diff)	ADF (stat)	Order integration
Y	-0.7014	ΔY	-6.2026***	I(1)
X ₁	2.0279	ΔX ₁	4.3804***-	I(1)
X ₂	-0.8585	ΔX ₂	-5.5078***	I(1)
X ₃	-0.1957	ΔX ₃	.4443***	I(1)
X ₄	-3.6918***	ΔX ₄		I(0)
X ₅	-1.1359	ΔX ₅	-7.8709***	I(1)
X ₆	-0.0751	ΔX ₆	-4.2520***	I(1)
X ₇	-1.2812	ΔX ₇	-8.0421***	I(1)
X ₈	-1.9345	ΔX ₈	-5.0035***	I(1)

Source: computed from field survey, 2017. * Significant level at 1% (-3.6463).

3.2.2 Bounds test for co-integration

Table 3 interprets the findings of Wald-test (F-Statistics) for a long-run relationship. As indicated on the table below the calculated F-statistics (3.81) is significantly higher than the upper bound critical value at a 5 and 1 percent level of significance. This implies that the null hypothesis of no co-integration is rejected at 5 and 1 percent significance level. Therefore a co-integrating relationship among the variables is confirmed.

Table 3: Results of Bound Test for Co-integration

Critical value	Upper bound	Lower bound
5%	3.15	2.11
1%	3.77	2.62

Computed F-statistic: 3.81, Critical Values at A = 8-1 =

3.2.3 Long- run estimates of the aggregate credit volume of agriculture within the interest cost of capital regulated and deregulated periods

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The long-run estimates showing the aggregate credit volume of agriculture within the interest rate or cost of capital regulated and deregulated periods are presented in Table 4. The result shows that the average interest lending rate (X_1) and government budget allocation (X_5) were the significant variables that had a long-run effect on the aggregate credit volume of agriculture. The coefficient of interest rate was negative (-1.0708) and statistically significant at 5%. This implies that an increase in interest rate will reduce the aggregate credit volume of agriculture. Conversely, government budget allocation had a positive (0.8284) and a significant effect on the aggregate credit volume of agriculture at 1%. This implies that an increase in government budget allocation will increase the aggregate credit volume of agriculture. The result obtained is in line with that of Onoja *et. al.*, (2013).

Table 4: Long-run estimate of aggregate credit volume of agriculture within the cost of capital regulated and deregulated periods.

Regressor	Coefficient	SE	Z- ratio
$\text{Ln}X_1$	-1.0708**	0.3976	-2.6936
$\text{Ln}X_2$	1.1668	0.6808	1.7140
$\text{Ln}X_3$	1.0822	1.2100	0.8943
$\text{Ln}X_4$	0.3343	0.2466	1.3555
$\text{Ln}X_5$	0.8284***	0.2362	3.5059
$\text{Ln}X_6$	-0.2070	1,3127	-0.1577
$\text{Ln}X_7$	-0.0461	0.2767	-0.1666
$\text{Ln}X_8$	-0.1618	0.2093	-0.7733
C	2.1185	10.4687	0.2024

Source: computed from field survey, 2017

3.2.4 Short-run estimates of the aggregate credit volume of agriculture within the cost of capital regulated and deregulated periods.

The short-run result of aggregate credit volume of agriculture within the interest rate regulated and deregulated periods is presented in Table 5. The coefficient of the error correction term (-0.9164) is negative and statistically significant at the I percent level. The negative and significant coefficient is an indication of the co-integrating relationship between aggregate credit volume of agriculture and its explanatory variables. The magnitude of the coefficient implies that 92 % of the disequilibrium caused by previous year's shocks converges back to the long-run equilibrium in the current year; this implies that the adjustments are high, to correct to the long term equilibrium. The result showed that average interest lending rate, previous year's average savings rate, savings mobilized by financial institutions, average inflation rate, government budget allocation to agriculture and credit to the private sector were the significant variables that have a short-run impact on aggregate credit volume of agriculture within the interest rate regulated and deregulated periods. Specifically, the coefficient of savings mobilized by financial institutions (3.8764), average inflation rate (0.3615) and government budget allocation to agriculture (0.5164) was positive and statistically significant at 1% respectively. This implies that an increase in savings mobilized by a financial institution, average inflation rate and government budget allocation to agriculture will have a positive effect on aggregate credit volume of agriculture. Furthermore, average interest lending rate (-0.3632), previous year's average savings rate(-0.6283) and credit to private sector all have a negative but significant effect on aggregate credit volume of agriculture within the interest rate regulated and deregulated periods at various level of significance. This implies that the aggregate credit volume of agriculture increases with a decrease in average interest lending rate, the previous year's average savings rate and credit to the private sector (-1.0829). The finding of this study is in line with that of Chinyere (2016), who obtained a negative long run relationship between the interest rate and investment in Nigeria. Similarly, Ene (2015) obtained a direct relationship between the interest rate and performance rate of the bank.

Table 5: Short -run estimates of the aggregate credit volume of agriculture within the cost of capital regulated and deregulated periods.

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Regressor	Coefficient	SE	z-ratio
$\Delta \text{Ln}X_1$	-0.3632	0.1732	-2.0965*
$\Delta \text{Ln}X_2$	-0.1876	0.3089	-0.6072
$\Delta \text{Ln}X_{2(-)}$	-0.6283	0.347^	-1.8078*
$\Delta \text{Ln}X_3$	3.8764	0.7017	5.5240***
$\Delta \text{Ln}X_4$	0.3615	0.1201	3.0086***
$\Delta \text{Ln}X_5$	0.5164	0.1144	4.5137***
$\Delta \text{Ln}X_6$	-1.0829	0.5861	-1.8474*
$\Delta \text{Ln}X_{6(-)}$	-2.1282	0.4778	-4.4548***
$\Delta \text{Ln}X_7$	-0.1052	0.1696	-0.6200
$\Delta \text{Ln}X_8$	-0.1589	0.2416	-0.6574
$\text{ECM}_{(-)}$	-0.9164	0.1138	-8.0459***

$$\text{Cointeq} = \text{LNY} - (-1,070\text{S}'\text{LNX1} + 1.1669''\text{LNX2} + 1.0822'\text{LNX3} + 0.3343 ''\text{LNX4} + 0.8284*\text{LNX5} - 0.2071 *\text{LNX6} - 0.046\text{TLNX7} - 0.1618*\text{LNX8} + \bullet 2.1186)$$

Significant levels *** = 1%, ** = 10%

Source: computed from field survey, 2017

3.2.5 Diagnostic tests

The regression for the underlying ARDL equation fits very well and also passes the diagnostic tests against, serial correlation, functional form misspecification, non-normal errors and heteroscedasticity as presented in Table 5.

Table 6: ARDL-VECM Model Diagnostic tests LM test statistic

LM test statistic			
Serial correlation	$\chi^2(1) = 3.6194 [0.1571]$	Normality	$\chi^2(2) = 1.9614 [0.3750]$
Functional form	$\chi^2(1) + 1.764 [0.184]$	Heteroscedasticity	$\chi^2(1) = 6.8093 [0.9859]$

Source: computed from field survey, 2017

4.0 Level of the real credit growth rate of agricultural finance in Nigeria

The level of the real credit growth rate of agricultural finance in Nigeria is shown in Table 7. Usually, the real growth rate takes into account the inflation rate at a given time and this study has taken this into account to estimate the level of the real growth rate of agricultural finance in Nigeria. By estimates, the agricultural credit growth rate increased in real terms at 8.91% under the period of study. This indicated that during this period, financial institutions, government and credit agencies supplied the sector with this percentage of credit. The result obtained from this study is higher than that of Onyishi, Arene & Ifora (2015) who had a value of 0.01% for credit growth rate in agricultural financing in Nigeria between 1970-2011.

More so, the finding showed that agricultural GDP contribution to the Nigerian economy had a positive relationship with credit volume to agriculture. This indicated that a 1% increase in agricultural credit would lead to 0.0014 % increase in agriculture's GDP contribution to the Nigerian economy. The result of this study affirmed the assertion of Onyishi, Arene & Ifora, (2015) that interest rate or cost of capital deregulation has a positive effect on economic growth.

Table 7: Level of real credit growth rate in agricultural financing in Nigeria (1982-2017)

Items	Rate/ Model
The real credit growth rate	8.91
Agricultures GDP contribution and credit volume relationship model	$= 1.4 \times 10^{-3}x + 1185.19$

Source: computed from field survey, 2017, Where Y = Agricultures GDP contribution to the Nigerian economy; X = Credit volume to agriculture

4.1 Effects of government finance interventions on agricultural sector performance in Nigeria

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The effects of government intervention in agriculture sector finance performance in the Nigerian economy are shown in Table 8. Results showed that about 95% of the total variation in agricultural sector performance was explained by variations in the explanatory variables used in the model. Results of agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme Fund (ACGSF) and loan were in line with the *a priori* expectation. This indicated that ACGSF and commercial bank loan (CBL) were major determinants of the government finance interventions on the agricultural sector and its contribution to the GDP of the Nigerian economy. It also implied that the larger the volume of credit by ACGSF and CBL, the greater the amount of credit to the agricultural sector.

Table 8 Effects of government finance interventions on agricultural sector performance in Nigeria

Variable	coefficient	standard error	t- test
Constant	522.76	325.026	1.61
AGSCF	0.000539	0.000104	5.16***
Loan	0.0339	0.002970	11.42***
R ²	0.95		
Adj.R ²	0.94		
f- statistics	303.95***		

Source: computed from field survey, *** = represents significance at 1%

5.0 Conclusion and Policy Recommendations

The study has examined increasing Agricultural Investments through Cost of Capital Deregulation in Nigeria, with the following specific objectives: ascertain the factors that determine aggregate credit volume of agricultural investment within the cost of regulated and deregulated periods and estimate the level of growth rate in agricultural financing in Nigeria before and after a deregulated period. Co-integration and Real Credit Growth Rate Model were used to realize the objectives respectively. The result showed that interest rate deregulation had a significant and positive impact on agricultural growth in Nigeria, there is a co-integrating relationship among the variables and average interest lending rate and government budget allocation were the significant variables that had a long-run effect on the aggregate credit volume. Result also showed that 92 % of the disequilibrium caused by previous year's shocks converges back to the long-run equilibrium in the current year. Credit volume of agriculture increases with a decrease in average interest lending rate, also agricultural credit growth rate increased in real terms at 8.91% under the period of study, while agricultural GDP contribution to Nigerian economy had a positive relationship with credit volume to agriculture. finally, ACGSF and CBL were major determinants of the government finance interventions on the agricultural sector and its contribution to the GDP of the Nigerian economy. The following recommendations are proffered: interest rate should be reduced to at least 5% or any other single digit to stimulate investment in the agricultural sector and there should be proper implementation, coordination, and evaluation of financial policies in the agricultural sector.

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